

POST-PRINT VERSION

Richard Woolley and Tim Turpin (2009) CV analysis as a complementary methodological approach: investigating the mobility of Australian scientists. *Research Evaluation*, 18(2): 143–151.

<https://doi.org/10.3152/095820209X441808>

Abstract

Human migration and geographic mobility of scientific and technical human capital are interwoven phenomena. Twin processes of human capital and social capital network formation through scientific mobility have been important for capacity building in the Asia-Pacific. This paper focuses on a sample of research participants from Australia, illustrating how CVs can enable methodological progress in filtering respondent survey data. In particular, CVs prove to be an effective data source for disentangling migration from scientific mobility, and in developing a stratified sample of forms of mobility for further qualitative data collection in this ongoing research. It is noted that CVs also show potential for appreciating collective processes of capital accumulation in the sciences, along with the durability of collective forms of organization, such as networks, over time.

A highly skilled science and technology workforce is regarded as an essential element of national innovation policies and programs oriented toward economic growth and social development (David and Foray, 2002; OECD, 2002; Powell and Snellman, 2004). Research into geographic mobility, as one aspect of the career dynamics of skilled scientific research workers, has thus become increasingly common as policy-makers try to assess their capacity to fill scientific and technological roles in national innovation systems. In this context mobility has come to be seen as a largely 'positive' value by research policy-makers.¹ Many countries have developed specific policies to try and attract and retain scientific researchers (Laudel, 2005; Zweig, 2006), taking the view that scientific mobility is at least to some extent a product of competition between nations and regions for the knowledge, skills and talents considered essential for knowledge-based innovation strategies (Johnson and Regets, 1998; Kleinman and Vallas, 2001; Powell and Snellman, 2004).

The understanding of skilled migration and mobility as competitive is partly a reflection of early economic analyses of movements of skilled human capital as a zero-sum game (Bhagwati, 1979; Bhagwati and Hamada, 1976). Developing countries were considered to have their human capital resources depleted by the flows of talented and skilled individuals to the developed world, particularly the United States (Committee on International Relations US House of Representatives, 1977). This has led global institutions to focus on questions of net 'brain gains' and 'brain drains' in relation to development and fairness (Dickson, 2003; Docquier and Rapoport, 2005; InterAcademy Council, 2004; OECD, 2002). It has also been argued that the 'brain drain' can have positive impacts on the circumstances of developing countries (Gaillard and Gaillard, 1997), including creating aspirations for education (Rapoport, 2002) and technology transfer through the return of scientists (Ozden and Schiff, 2005). As the geographic mobility of the highly skilled generally can involve combinations of professional factors and other personal or political reasons for migration, other researchers have argued that 'circulation' is a better way of conceptualizing such movements and their varied temporalities, complexity and fluidity (Ackers, 2005; Iredale and Appleyard, 2001).

No comprehensive theory of scientific mobility has emerged. Nonetheless, the zero-sum understanding of human capital mobility has been challenged by research and theory emerging from a range of fields concerned, at least to some extent, with the movement of highly skilled scientific personnel. These fields include innovation studies (Coe and Bunnell, 2003), labour studies (Williams, 2007), national innovation systems analysis (Hart, 2007), migration studies (Ackers, 2005), sociological studies of science (Laudel, 2005) and science policy analysis (Fontes, 2007). Current research into scientific mobility also reflects the expanded geographic circulation of talented researchers, particularly toward Asia (Goldbrunner *et al*, 2006; Zweig, 2006). The contemporary mobility of scientists has come to be understood as both a driver and a consequence of processes of organizing knowledge production and distribution, which are argued to be both increasingly globalized (Mahroum, 2000) and diversified (Gibbons *et al*, 1994; Kleinman and Vallas, 2001).

This globalized context is said to be characterized by the frequent back and forth movement of migrants, ideas, knowledge, information, and skill sets that is now a routine part of contemporary transnationalism. (Favell *et al*, 2007). In thinking about transnational mobility dynamics in this extended way, Coe and Bunnell (2003: 454) have

argued for a 'network ontology' centred on the circulation of innovative personnel and knowledge, in preference to 'scalar' approaches tied to fixed work sites or geographic locations. Indeed, network approaches to the distribution of researchers and knowledge have emerged, particularly to highlight linkages between scientists based in developed countries and their compatriots in developing ones, arguing that inter-connections can contribute to solving some of the human resource and economic growth issues confronting both poorer and richer countries (Barré *et al*, 2003; Meyer, 2001; Meyer and Wattiaux, 2006; Mahroum and De Guchteneire, 2006). As Meyer and Wattiaux have put it, the conceptual definition and growing empirical analyses of 'diaspora' or 'distributed knowledge networks' (DKNs) have to some extent: subverted the traditional 'brain drain' migration outflow into a 'brain gain' skills circulation by converting the loss of human resources into a remote although accessible asset of expanded networks. (Meyer and Wattiaux 2006: 5).

Empirical studies of the functioning of these distributed knowledge networks have so far focused primarily on networks in the Americas (Meyer *et al*, 2001) and Africa (Meyer *et al*, 1999). A key observation is that networks of scientific and technological personnel may create positive externalities that boost the innovative capacity of developing countries by providing readily accessible new knowledge, ideas, technologies and skills.

Understanding the role of spatial mobility in network formation and the distribution of such 'positive externalities' is linked to the broader problem of tracing the mobility of scientific researchers, which has challenged social scientists internationally (OECD, 2002). Research into diaspora knowledge networks has used an electronic and website-based communications methodology (Meyer and Brown, 1999; Meyer and Wattiaux, 2006), while the OECD has considered a survey and indicators approach to mapping the mobility of PhDs (Auriol *et al*, 2007). Biao (2005) used 130 CVs of overseas Chinese professionals as background information in a study of diaspora networks and knowledge exchange.

None of these methodologies is directed toward the connection between geographic mobility and the (trans)formation of DKNs. Understanding the way mobility pathways unfold over time requires comprehensive longitudinal and sequential data. The compiling of such information in one location is one of the major advantages of CVs as data sources (Dietz *et al*, 2000). As a tool for investigating geographic mobility and the emergence and elaboration of DKNs then, CV analysis appears an attractive option, as CVs are effectively a record of mobility through social, organizational and geographic space. This paper reflects on the use of CVs to study the interlinked phenomena of scientific mobility and the emergence and elaboration of distributed knowledge networks. Following the scientific and technical human capital (STHC) approach (Bozeman *et al*, 2001), it conceives of such networks as an organization form of collective and cumulative capacity building in science. CV analysis has been used as part of an ongoing mixed-methods study of scientific mobility in the Asia-Pacific region. The study has focused on the role of research training (postgraduate) and early career research positions (postdoctorate) in the formation of research networks and collaborations. The analysis of CVs has provided a bridging methodological step between a large-scale survey and the framing of samples of researchers for further qualitative study of the mobility of Australian scientists.

First, CVs have been used to try and disentangle migratory and scientific mobilities among Australian participants. In this respect CVs provide a method for investigating the position of Australia in relation to both inflows and outflows of researchers. This also allows for comprehension of the relative permanence and transience of some of these moves. Second, CVs have been used to categorize predominantly domestically based Australian participants as relatively high, moderate or low mobility.

Using these two approaches a stratified sample of researchers has been identified for qualitative data collection. As will be described below, this process has been accomplished with reference to the aim of including within the sample a balance of cases that are representative of the major patterns of movement identified in the survey, while also incorporating cases of researchers whose relatively highly levels of mobility would have remained concealed if the selection process had relied solely on the survey results.

Network building and the mobility of scientific and technical human capital

Mahroum (2000: 367) describes 'scientific mobility' as movement that proceeds 'through channels of institutions that enjoy a high reputation for excellence and expertise'. Research training and postdoctoral positions can be understood in this way, as proceeding through such 'institutional channels' which operate as 'mobility mechanisms' (Coe and Bunnell, 2003) for the movement of scientists between organizations and countries. As Melin (2004) has described in relation to a sample of Swedish scientists undertaking postdocs abroad, this mobility can operate to 'integrate' researchers from different countries. However, this integration often follows patterns 'inherited' from older generations of scientific mentors and supervisors, through institutions in leading Western science centres, but without necessarily leading to 'exploratory' science or expanded geographical distributions (Melin, 2004). However, such pathways of international mobility may often intersect in locations such as the USA, for example, connecting European researchers with those circulating from Asia-Pacific (Turpin *et al*, 2008). Researchers who move through these channels can be conceptualized as 'network builders', who establish social connections and personalized relationships that endure beyond their tenure in particular places.

A conception of mobile researchers as 'network builders' resonates with the approach taken by Bozeman *et al* (2001) in developing the concept of 'scientific and technical human capital' (STHC). The concept of STHC (Bozeman *et al*, 2001: 718) pairs an 'expanded notion of human capital' with a 'productive social capital network' to build a model of knowledge creation and innovation. In particular, the STHC model gives less attention to the discrete products and immediate outcomes from scientific projects and programs and more attention to scientists' career trajectories and their sustained ability to contribute and enhance their capabilities (Bozeman *et al*, 2001: 718). The STHC model is based around the interplay between individual accumulations of *human capital* and collective distributions of *social capital*, a process that is 'so fundamental, intimate, and dynamic that neither concept is fully meaningful by itself' (Bozeman *et al*, 2001: 723).

Understanding mobility as a process through which individuals seek to simultaneously enhance their individual (human capital) capabilities but also to become integrated into, and build, research collectives and professional connections (social capital) integrates mobility into the theoretical framework of STHC. Due to the collective and social nature of scientific practice (Bozeman *et al*, 2001: 724–725) these activities are in a fundamental

sense indivisible. Hence our interest in relationships between destinations for research training, postdoctoral research (human capital accumulation), and the formation of research networks and knowledge-producing collaborations (social capital accumulation). The concept of 'scientific mobility' can thus be expanded and understood also as processes through which capabilities (human capital) and capacities (social capital) are augmented, in this case through integration into, and elaboration of, distributed knowledge networks that are at once both professional and personalized (Wellman, 2001).

A researcher's CV can be understood, from the STHC perspective, as a record of processes of capital accumulation. As these processes are both individual and collective, as described above, CVs contain traces of both relatively individualized human capital accumulation (e.g. qualifications) and relatively collective social capital accumulation (e.g. collaborative grants), which are neither purely one nor the other. As described, we have been investigating DKNs as products of scientists' mobile 'network building' activity, as a particular form of collectivization that relies on the formation and maintenance of professional *and* personal connections through periods of collocation. Geographic mobility can thus enrich individuals but also expand the dispersed collectivities in which they become personally involved. This is a relatively delimited conceptualization, of a collectivity based on some level of personal connection and interaction no matter how transient, infrequent or distant.

The relationship between mobility and the accumulation of human and social capital is undoubtedly complex and multi-dimensional. There are a number of different dimensions of scientific mobility besides the spatial or geographic, including sectoral, intellectual or organizational mobilities. Each may constitute qualitatively distinct opportunities to enhance capabilities and to build a 'productive social capital network'. A researcher's CV provides an opportunity to identify and categorize a range of different mobilities as a way of evaluating just how 'mobile' an individual researcher has been throughout their career in the process of accumulating capital and building networks. The opportunities for accumulation of capital can, at least theoretically, be analysed in terms of both individual and collective dimensions, in the cases of co-authorships and collaborative grants, for example. From our perspective of investigating relationships between specifically *geographic or spatial* mobility and DKNs, CV analysis provided important methodological opportunities that are described below. However, as Bozeman *et al* (2001: 733) describe in relation to measuring STHC capacity, the CV is to some extent a 'starting point' for an investigation of network-building activity and geographic mobility. It is anticipated that using CVs to identify a sample for qualitative research is likely to lead back to further interrogation of CVs, in concert with bibliometric and other forms of analyses.

Investigating Australian scientists' mobility

The authors have been studying the mobility of scientists from the Asia-Pacific region in relation to the building of distributed knowledge networks (DKNs). The central research question guiding the study has been to investigate whether destinations for undertaking research training (PhD) and postdoctoral research (P-doc) are involved in building research networks and collaboration. In the major data collection of the project, an online survey was conducted with authors drawn from the Science Citation Index (SCI) in 2005 who were working in 22 countries across the Asia-Pacific. A total of 10,300 responses were received.

In one of the main sections of the survey, participants were asked a series of questions about their networks and the research collaborations in which they were involved. These included:

- The major locations of participants' research networks;
- The countries in which they had spent most time working as science researchers; and
- The location of collaborators on the most important example of transnational knowledge production in which they had participated.

Statistical analyses were conducted showing positive and significant correlations at an aggregate level between locations for PhDs and postdocs and the distribution of networks and collaborations (Turpin *et al*, 2008). These correlations varied somewhat in strength, but were consistently positive and significant across different nationalities and scientific disciplines (Turpin *et al*, 2008). These results supported the hypothesis that destinations for postgraduate training and postdoctoral research play a role in the structuring of DKNs.

The survey instrument allowed for respondents, who were otherwise anonymous, to offer their names for a subsequent call from the project team to participate in further aspects of the research. A very high proportion of respondents responded favourably to this request (82%). Following this positive response, the project entered a second phase of selecting cases for qualitative data collection with Australian-based respondents with a postgraduate research qualification ($n = 920$). It is in the process of selecting a stratified sample for this second phase that CV analysis was used as a complementary methodology:

- To disentangle migratory inflows and scientific mobility among Australian respondents; and
- To identify relatively high, moderate and low mobility respondents.

A small data collection was undertaken to pilot this phase of the research. Full CVs were requested via email from 250 Australian survey respondents aged 50 years and older, who were currently working in Australia. The reason for choosing older participants for the pilot study was the probability of greater amounts of information and to assess the consistency of the data contained across the course of a relatively long career. Seventeen of the 250 contact emails were not deliverable. A total of 80 CVs were received, 79 by return email and one by post. This represented a response rate of 34.3%, suggesting approximately 300 CVs could be anticipated from a full call to the Australian survey respondents. Of the CVs received, 58% were from scientists whose current major appointment was within a university, 34% from those in government organizations and 8% from those working in business.

Using CV analysis as a complementary methodology for investigating mobility

The first stage of working with the CVs as a complementary methodology entailed relating the types of information contained with different dimensions of researcher mobility. A categorization of types of CV information by dimensions of mobility is shown in Table 1. These dimensions and the associated CV data require little additional description with the possible exception of 'intellectual mobility' (Shinn and Benguigui, 1997), which refers to transformation or transference of the kinds of questions or fields of inquiry that guide a researcher's activity.

As Table 1 shows, CVs contain a number of indicators of geographic mobility. All of these can provide important complementary information, depending on the research questions being addressed and the base information the CV data is to complement. For example, our survey database contains only the country in which qualifications were gained and employment undertaken. CV data goes to a greater level of detail by naming host institutions for education and employer organizations. Although outside the scope of the pilot study, this level of granularity makes analyses by factors such as institution rankings or organization size a possibility. In relation to our research aims, CVs provide additional data on employment locations and their sequencing not available from the project survey. The survey database also contains no information on visits or conferences, so these two types of information are new data that can be added to each individual's survey record where included in the CV in sufficient detail.

Table 1. Mobility indicators in CVs

Mobility dimension	CV data indicator
Geographic	Undergraduate degree location Research training (PhD) location Postdoctoral research position location Employment locations Visits Conferences
Sectoral	Employer organization type
Organizational	Promotions Changes in functional role
Intellectual	Qualifications fields Field of publication Sources of research funding

Indicators of geographic mobility can also provide an opportunity for understanding the contribution of specific forms of mobility to individual and collective processes of capital accumulation in science. As described earlier, research training and postdoctoral positions have important network-building functions (Melin, 2004; Turpin *et al*, 2008) that can augment STHC capacity over time. CVs offer the potential to analyse subsequent mobilities, particularly for employment or formal visits, that may be vital to the maintenance of the collaborative activity established through movements through institutional channels for training or post-doctoral work. Patterns of repeated visits can be coded as evidence of the role of continuing collocation in processes of collaboration. At the same time, exploring these mobility indicators may also give insights into emergent networks, which can complement analyses of collaborative publishing or patenting activity. Such mobilities may therefore be important indicators of both the emergence and

durability of networks over time, and hence to their function in collective forms of capital accumulation.

Disentangling migration and scientific mobility

Australia is a country of high immigration levels, which in recent years has increased the emphasis on the skilled stream within the overall migration program (DIAC, 2008). The survey database contains information on a single identifier of origin: 'nationality'. In designing the survey instrument, this was viewed as preferable to asking about 'country of birth' as it increased the flexibility that an individual had in nominating where they currently viewed their 'home' location to be. Unfortunately, the concise nature of the survey did not provide scope to accommodate those participants with dual nationality. In the Australian context a methodological problem subsequently arose, as a significant proportion of those nominating their nationality as 'Australian' will be either dual nationals or will have forgone the nationality acquired by virtue of the country of their birth, which may also be the country responsible for the investments in their education and research training — a factor important to identify in mobility studies. For example, large numbers of (particularly older) researchers and scholars in all fields in Australian universities are British-born and -educated and have subsequently migrated to Australia on a permanent basis. The disentangling of inflows and outflows and their timing in relation to training and employment were thus viewed as important for understanding various patterns of Australian scientists' mobilities, and potentially for the study of diaspora network involvements.

In working with the survey data, Australian respondents who were awarded their undergraduate degree in Australia and PhD overseas were assumed to be Australian-born and -educated individuals whose geographic movement could be more properly termed 'scientific mobility'. However, a methodological problem existed in distinguishing whether an Australian scientist educated overseas acquired their qualifications prior to migrating to Australia, or by travelling to an overseas destination from Australia. The potential significance of this issue was suggested by comparing the proportion of Australian respondents with an overseas undergraduate degree (23.6%) with proportions for respondents from other Asia-Pacific locations including PR China (2.9%), India (1.6%), Japan (1.9%), Korea (6.3%) and Taiwan (7.8%). These data suggested that the Australian survey respondents may be drawn from a relatively wide range of backgrounds and that many may have moved to Australia after gaining their undergraduate qualification.

To clarify these data, each CV was first compared with the matched survey record to ensure that locations of qualifications were consistent between the two data sources. Once these data were validated, each CV was allocated to one of four categories summarized in Table 2.

Due to the location of their undergraduate degree award, the CVs of respondents in Group A and Group B (n = 24) were checked for information on place of birth. Eighteen of the CVs had a specific item on place of birth and in all these cases the respondent was born overseas and had migrated to Australia. Six CVs did not specify place of birth; three from Group B had arrived in Australia for the purpose of undertaking postgraduate research training and had subsequent continuous employment and other appointments in Australia. The three CVs from Group A that did not specify place of birth all indicated the respondent had moved from employment overseas to a new job in Australia. Five CVs in

Group C and Group D indicated the respondent had been born overseas and moved to Australia prior to their undergraduate degree. These cases were subsequently treated as products of the domestic (Australian) education system.

Table 2. Location of qualifications awarded, selected Australian survey respondents, aged 50+ and working in Australia (n = 80)

Undergrad overseas Postgrad overseas (Group A)	Undergrad overseas Postgrad Australia (Group B)	Undergrad Australia Postgrad overseas (Group C)	Undergrad Australia Postgrad Australia (Group D)
20%	10%	15%	55%

The analysis of these diverse migratory flows added two significant types of information to the process of selecting a sample of researchers for qualitative data collection. The first of these was in relation to timing of moves that resulted in migration. The timing of the move to Australia was coded for each case as being:

- For postgraduate research training;
- To take up a postdoctoral research position; or
- For other professional employment.

Inward migratory movements were thus coded in terms of the key mobility mechanisms (PhDs, P- docs) involved in network building, as defined in the broader study.

The second type of information coded was the country of origin of the researcher. Where this was different from the location for undergraduate degree, this information could be important for understanding the start point for mobility processes. In particular, analysis of CVs led to the identification of three cases where individuals from the Asian region appeared to have been mobile for undergraduate training. This is to be expected, particularly among older scientists, as teaching and research training has historically been unevenly distributed across the Asia-Pacific region. Identification of such mobilities is particularly important in selecting a sample for qualitative data collection as it implies opportunities to investigate the extent to which DKNs may extend not just through PhD-training and postdoctoral re- search locations but also back to countries of origin. This identification could not have occurred without the complementary data provided via CVs.

In summary, using CV analysis as a complementary methodology to try and disentangle migratory movements and scientific mobilities in selecting a sample of researchers for qualitative research was effective in three ways. First, migratory flows assumed in the survey data on undergraduate degree location were able to be validated. This enables a stratified sample to be drawn from both overseas- born Australian researchers (Groups A and B) and the Australian-born (Groups C and D). Second, distinctions were able to be drawn in terms of the timing of migratory moves. The qualitative sample can thus be stratified to include those who have migrated through channels of education, for research and for employment. This implies migratory moves associated with researchers at different points in their re- search trajectory and with different accruals of STHC. This provides further variation and comparative opportunities for investigating geographic mobilities and DKNs. Finally, analysis of CVs enabled the identification of cases of particular interest in relation to investigating network connections between scientists from developing and developed countries in the region.

Identifying different mobilities among Australian researchers

The major limitation of the survey data in terms of understanding the relationship between geographic mobility and network-building activity were the limited number of data points that pinpoint the actual location of the researcher at a particular stage of their career. Although the location of some major markers of career formation (gaining qualifications) and progress (postdoctoral research, current position) were captured in the survey, these data are manifestly inadequate for understanding the role of spatial mobility in career trajectories beyond identifying a basic triangle (PhD–Postdoc–Current job). CVs were thus used to add more mobility data points to the records of Australian educated researchers (Groups C and D in Table 2).

A majority (70%) of the contributors to the pilot study were Australian-born and -educated to the level of undergraduate degree. Researchers in Group C were identified from the survey as having been mobile for research training. Of these, half had moved back to Australia in their entry into the labour market. Of those who remained overseas, half moved to a second country, in all cases to take up a postdoctoral research position. Categorizing Group C into three separate mobility patterns was considered a sufficient basis for selecting a stratified sample from among these mobile researchers. The additional data points added to these records did not provide any further differentiation or reveal individual cases of particular interest.

A majority of respondents (55%) also did their re- search training (PhD) in Australia (Group D). From the point of the view of the survey data these respondents appeared the least mobile. The first task of analysing the CVs of respondents in Group D was therefore to discover the extent of any ‘hidden’ geo- graphic mobility, that is, mobility that was not captured by the survey. The geographic mobility of the Australian-educated and -trained respondents was analysed using three variables: postdoctoral research destination; employment destinations; and visits. The objective was to identify researchers who had been relatively geographically mobile across their careers and those who had not as part of developing a stratified sample. At the same time, each individual case was also coded in terms of the regional focus of the movements identified.

Postdoctoral positions and employment are almost always included on Australian researchers’ CVs un- der the same heading, usually professional appointments or employment. In terms of data quality, 94% of the CVs had comprehensive data on appointments and employment including start and end dates. Where the survey record of the respondent indicated that they had held a postdoctoral research position this was validated by referring to the CV. Once these data were validated all postdoctoral positions and jobs were coded in the same way. Each position that required a move to a different country was given a score of one point, with a further point added for each year of the appointment. For example, a position that involved moving from Australia to Singa- pore for a three-year period was coded as a 4. A subsequent move within Singapore for another three-year appointment was coded as a 3. Moving back to Australia was coded as a 1, for the movement alone. Although a very ‘rough and ready’ measure, this was viewed as sufficient for the simple discrimination between cases being sought. The results of this scoring exercise are shown in Figure 1.

The coding exercise performed a useful function in highlighting relative levels of geographic mobility among this small group of Australian respondents (all 50+ years, 15% female) not evident from the survey data. Almost 40% of these respondents had spent no time working outside Australia. A similar proportion had spent up to five years in a

maximum of two overseas jobs. A smaller number had worked outside Australia for longer, in a maximum of three different jobs. Selection of relatively geographically mobile cases for qualitative data collection could proceed via a more detailed analysis of the high-scoring cases identified using this simple procedure. However, to search for other 'hidden' mobility a further variable, visits, was also coded.

The main problem with coding visits was the inconsistency of the coverage of information on this type of geographic mobility in the CVs received. Only 40% of the CVs (Group C and D) included data on visits and of these only one-quarter included detailed data with start and end dates. Despite these problems, visits were coded in terms of a single point for every visit to an overseas institution, reflecting frequency of mobility rather than the duration of stays overseas. The process of coding the available data proved to be important in relation to the objective of finding 'hidden' mobilities not identified through either the survey data or analysis of CV data on employment.

Three individual cases stood out in this regard. The first individual was from Group C and had been a postdoctoral researcher at the same institution where their PhD was awarded. After returning to Australia for their next job, this researcher had remained employed at the same institution for the next three decades. During this period the researcher had undertaken 31 visits of a minimum of one month in length. These visits were primarily to a small number of destinations in North America, but also to PR China and Europe on several occasions (but did not include the PhD/postdoc institution). The high level and particular patterns of this mobility meant this individual was of particular interest and would be included in the sample to be approached to participate in qualitative research.

Two cases from Group D also drew attention due to their high level of mobility through visits. The first individual had never worked outside Australia and had in fact been employed in the same public sector position for more than 30 years. During this period, however, the researcher had been highly internationally mobile, having undertaken 24 visits listed on the CV, to Asia, Africa, North America, Latin America and Europe. These visits were to conduct research in university or government laboratories or to consult/advise. The second individual had also never been employed outside Australia, although this researcher had changed organizations on four occasions within Australia in the course of a 23-year professional career. CV data revealed that this researcher was also highly mobile, having undertaken 12 visits of up to four months' duration in the past decade, mainly to North American universities.

The grants and publications records of both these researchers further indicated consistent international collaboration on research and knowledge production (co-authorship) activities. Both had sustained patterns of geographic mobility, which appear likely to have been integral to these professional relationships. Both would therefore be cases of considerable interest for qualitative data collection. In both cases, network-building activities would appear to be based on regular short-term geographic movements rather than the more sustained involvements characteristic of periods of research training or employment. There may be particular implications for the building and maintaining of distributed knowledge networks that are associated with this kind of mobile activity. These implications could be investigated via interviews.

Figure 1. Mobility scores, selected Australian respondents (Group D) (n = 42)

Discussion

The pilot exercise found CVs to be a useful source of information on the career trajectory, capital accumulation strategies and mobilities of research participants, complementing data collected through a survey on geographic mobility and the building of DKNs. In working with the survey records of a sub-sample of Australian respondents, CVs were very useful for clarifying researcher origins, revealing potential for more subtle disentangling of ‘scientific mobility’ and migratory aspects of the geographic movement of STHC. The coding exercise undertaken also revealed ‘hidden mobilities’ not captured in the survey, but which appeared directly relevant to the study’s key research questions. CVs were thus instrumental in selecting a stratified sample for qualitative work that was both representative of prominent patterns of mobility evident in the survey data, but also sensitive to identifying cases of distinctive mobilities.

Network building involves simultaneous individual and collective accumulation of capital. The pilot exercise prompted reflection on the possibility of coding types of collective accumulation of human and social capital that are indicators of the emergence and development of DKNs. Co-authorship data are the obvious indicator of such collective processes, but are best analysed using other tools available through electronic databases. However, visits to other institutions, hosting visiting researchers and exchanges of students are examples of types of network-building processes that collectively accumulate STHC and can be associated with geo- graphic mobility.

There were observable problems with the cover- age and detail of data types, such as visits and collaborative grants, which are relevant indicators of the collective accumulation of capital in the CVs we worked with. However, other methodological possibilities, such as recruiting the CVs of research collaborators and network associates, could increase the amount of available detail, validate data and thereby enhance the study of processes of collective accumulation of capital. The building of relatively durable DKNs could be studied, by analysing the way the collective

accumulation of capital is reproduced and evolves over time. A systematic analysis of these collective accumulations of capital over time could also highlight the role of geographic mobility in the maintenance of relatively consolidated networks. As a record of human and social capital accumulation processes that irreducibly involve both the enhancing of individual capabilities and the expansion of collective capacities, CVs appear to have significant potential for studying the emergence and development of DKNs, beyond the kind of instrumental methodological purpose described in this paper.

Note

1. For example, Australia has embarked on a policy of participating in 'brain circulation' to ensure that 'our brightest researchers are exposed to cutting edge research environments so that they can bring this knowledge and skill back to Australia', while creating skilled migration and education pathways for migrants 'leaving their country of origin to seek opportunities in Australia' (DEST, 2006: 67–68)

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